

Проблема оценки качества подготовки государственных гражданских служащих: личностные и профессиональные характеристики

В. Б. САЛАХОВА, А. В. КИДИНОВ, Н. С. БАБИЕВА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение. Современный мир требует подготовки и непрерывного развития кадров в системе государственного управления новой формации, способных успешно адаптироваться к стремительно изменяющимся условиям и быстро реагировать на риски, вызовы и угрозы, как внутренние (организационные), так и внешние (социально-экономические). Совершенствование системы оценки кадрового обеспечения государственной гражданской службы, развитие перспективных направлений трансформации интеллектуального капитала кадров государственного управления и администрирования, внедрение инноваций в процесс отбора, оценки и развития кадров государственного управления невозможно без комплексного научно-методологического обоснования данной проблемы.

Цель исследования: разработка комплексной системы оценки профессиональных и личностных качеств государственных гражданских служащих в системе государственного управления.

Материалы и методы. Методом исследования являлся теоретический анализ научной литературы по проблеме оценки профессиональных и личностных качеств государственных гражданских служащих; анализ нормативной правовой базы, регулирующей проведение оценки профессиональных и личностных качеств государственных гражданских служащих. Базой исследования выступили реферативные базы данных рецензируемой научной литературы: eLIBRARY.ru, lens.org; кроссплатформенная справочная правовая система – КонсультантПлюс.

Результаты. Развитие государственной гражданской службы в Российской Федерации должно быть связано с внедрением новых кадровых технологий в систему государственного управления, в частности комплексной системы оценки профессиональных и личностных качеств государственных гражданских служащих. Комплексная система оценки профессиональных и личностных качеств государственных гражданских служащих должна обеспечивать наиболее целесообразный, с точки зрения целей и задач государственного органа, перспективный отбор высококвалифицированных кадров для государственной службы. Разработана авторская модель комплексной системы оценки профессиональных и личностных качеств государственных гражданских служащих, реализация которой позволит оценить 1) уровень профессионального развития государственных гражданских служащих, 2) соответствие уровня развития профессиональных компетенций требуемой (занимаемой) должности, 3) профессиональный и личностный потенциал для карьерного роста. Практическая значимость исследования заключается в том, что предложенная комплексная система оценки профессиональных и личностных качеств государственных гражданских служащих может быть использована в практике государственного управления с целью получения объективных данных об уровне развития кадрового потенциала для совершенствования системы государственного управления, ориентированной на инновационное развитие российской экономики.

Заключение. Комплексная система оценки профессиональных и личностных качеств государственных гражданских служащих должна являться неотъемлемой частью процесса оценки KPI (результативности и эффективности деятельности) государственных служащих.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

профессиональные и личностные качества, государственные гражданские служащие, методология оценки, показатели эффективности и результативности деятельности, нормативные правовые акты

Для цитирования: Салахова В. Б., Кидинов А. В., Бабиева Н. С. Проблема оценки качества подготовки государственных гражданских служащих: личностные и профессиональные характеристики // Перспективы науки и образования. 2025. № 3. С. 588–606. <https://doi.org/10.32744/pse.2025.3.39>

Поступила: 07.12.2024 | Одобрена: 06.02.2025 | Опубликовано: 30.06.2025

Лицензия «С указанием авторства — С сохранением условий». Позволяет перерабатывать, исправлять и развивать произведения при условии указания авторства и лицензирования производных работ на аналогичных условиях.

The problem of assessing professional and personal qualities of public civil servants: socio-psychological aspect

V. B. SALAKHOVA, A. V. KIDINOV, N. S. BABIEVA

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The modern world requires training and continuous development of personnel in the system of public administration of a new formation, capable of successfully adapting to rapidly changing conditions and quickly responding to risks, challenges, and threats, both internal (organizational) and external (socio-economic). Improvement of the system of assessment of personnel supply of the state civil service, development of promising directions of transformation of intellectual capital of public administration and management personnel, introduction of innovations in the process of selection, assessment and development of public administration personnel is impossible without a comprehensive scientific and methodological substantiation of this problem.

The purpose of the study to develop a comprehensive system of assessment of professional and personal qualities of public civil servants in the system of public administration.

Materials and methods. The research method was theoretical analysis of scientific, educational and periodical literature on the stated problem; analysis of the regulatory legal framework governing the assessment of professional and personal qualities of public civil servants. The research was based on modern reference databases of peer-reviewed scientific literature: eLIBRARY.ru, lens.org; cross-platform reference legal system – ConsultantPlus.

Results. As a result of the conducted research the conclusions are made that the development of the state civil service in the Russian Federation should be associated with the introduction of new personnel technologies in the system of public administration and management, in particular, a comprehensive system of assessment of professional and personal qualities of state civil servants. A comprehensive system of assessment of professional and personal qualities of public civil servants should ensure the most appropriate from the point of view of the goals and objectives of the state body or its structural subdivision perspective selection of highly qualified personnel for public service. The author's model of the complex system of assessment of professional and personal qualities of public civil servants has been developed, the realization of which will allow assessing 1) the level of professional development of public civil servants, 2) conformity of the level of development of professional competencies to the required (occupied) position, 3) professional and personal potential for career growth. The practical significance of the study lies in the fact that the proposed comprehensive system of assessment of professional and personal qualities of public civil servants can be used in the practice of public administration to obtain objective data on the level of development of human resources to improve the system of public administration focused on the innovative development of the Russian economy.

Conclusion. A comprehensive system for assessing the professional and personal qualities of civil servants should be an integral part of the process of assessing KPIs (performance and efficiency) of civil servants.

KEYWORDS

professional and personal qualities, public civil servants, assessment methodology, indicators of efficiency and effectiveness of activity, regulatory legal sphere

For Citation: Salakhova, V. B., Kidinov, A. V., & Babieva, N. S. (2025). The problem of assessing professional and personal qualities of public civil servants: socio-psychological aspect. *Perspektivy nauki i obrazovaniya = Perspectives of Science and Education*, (3), 588–606. <https://doi.org/10.32744/pse.2025.3.39>

Received: 7 December 2024 | Approved: 6 February 2025 | Published: 30 June 2025

This is an open access article distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike International License (CC-BY-SA 4.0) that allows others to share the work with an acknowledgement of the work's authorship and initial publication in this journal

INTRODUCTION

In the period of worldwide globalization and digitalization of socio-economic and political systems around the world, the need to form and develop an effective system of public strategic administration is urgent. In terms of performance, human potential in management systems plays a decisive role [2]. This is since the effectiveness of selection of employees regarding the requirements and necessary competencies; the success of adaptation of employees to a new place of work (social and psychological); the probation period; the level and direction of motivation; training and development of employees; employee performance appraisal and personnel decisions depend on the efficiency and effectiveness of any department or institution [33].

Today there is no doubt that the main and the main driving force of social and economic development of any state is a person. There is a stable understanding in economics that the quality of the established management system at the state level determines the efficiency of its development [16]. However, the main reason for the low efficiency of economic activity, as well as the leading factor of its achievements, according to several researchers, is precisely the personality of the manager (manager), leadership style, as well as the degree or level of competence of the manager. For example, D. A. Butashin in his research points out the necessity of rotation of civil servants depending on their personal results [7]. Y. V. Sinyagin (the founder of assessment in Russian practice) in his numerous works develops the idea of the importance of individual and personal qualities of civil servants [38]. E. V. Lobkova and E. R. Khudonogova in their work substantiate the need to assess the professional and personal qualities of employees of public administration bodies [27]. Nevertheless, to achieve the goals of socio-economic development in the context of global digitalization and increasing competitiveness, it is not enough to have a set of certain professional competencies. The modern world requires training and continuous development of personnel in the public administration system of a new formation, capable of successfully adapting to rapidly changing conditions and quickly responding to risks and challenges, both internal (organizational) and external (socio-economic) [23]. For example, J. Albrecht, M. Robayo-Abril and S. Vroman justify the need for an out-of-door sourcing model to analyse the interaction between labour markets in the private and public sectors [1]. G. A. Borshchevskiy argues that «the effectiveness of personnel policy is measured by the level of utilisation of the personnel potential of the public sector to achieve the country's national goals. In the author's opinion, 'selection to the personnel reserves of civilian agencies should be centralised and removed from departmental subordination, and cases of hiring not from the reserve should be significantly limited. The role of experts in the selection of candidates should be expanded. The reserve should be formed not only by categories and groups of positions, but also by areas and types of professional service activities. The practice of interdepartmental appointments from the reserve and filling vacancies in subordinate organisations of the authorities should be formed» [6, p. 35]. A. G. Komissarov and I. B. Sheburakov in their work point out the necessity of 1) conducting personal and professional diagnostics of candidates for public service and 2) providing the results of the diagnostics. «Application of personal and professional diagnostics of civil servants provides targeted adjustment to the development of personal and professional qualities» [24, p. 19].

In the period of Russia's innovative development, the task of substantive and functional modernization of the system of assessment and development of a new generation of public civil servants, corresponding to the strategic goals and objectives of the modern world, becomes more and more urgent. Improvement of the system of assessment of civil service staffing, development of promising areas of transformation of intellectual capital of public administration and management personnel, introduction of innovations in the process of selection, assessment and development of public administration personnel is impossible, in turn, without a comprehensive scientific and methodological substantiation of this problem.

The analysis of modern studies devoted to solving organizational and managerial problems in the field of public administration allows us to say that there is still no unified methodology of comprehensive assessment of civil service personnel; unified technological and methodological support of the management process related to the formation and development of professional.

It should also be noted that the effectiveness of the management system of the subject's activity (in the context of our study - public authorities), regardless of the conditions and sphere of activity, depends on two groups of factors: 1) factors that include the peculiarities of socio-economic

environment development and 2) directly, the human factor [26]. The importance of these factors is explained by the fact that they play a determining role in achieving tactical and strategic goals of the organization as a system. It is these factors that contribute to the accumulation, development and transformation of resources necessary for effective and efficient activity of any organization. Consequently, the human resource potential of the organization represents the leading productive force of the organization, the consideration of the features of which is necessary when planning and implementing organizational activities [37].

Thus, the task of developing theoretical provisions; methodological and methodological foundations; innovative managerial and personalized approaches to the formation and effective functioning of the system of assessment and development of public administration personnel is of paramount importance today.

The modern system of evaluation of public administration personnel in our country is applied strictly based on the principles enshrined in the Russian legislation. This situation is explained by the need to ensure national security of the state in general and compliance with the law on personal data, in particular. However, the existing normative legal framework, firstly, does not regulate the activities related to the assessment of professional and personal qualities of public civil servants, secondly, does not contain a unified methodology for assessing the PLQ of civil service subjects, thirdly, reduces personnel assessment to mechanical testing for compliance with this or that position. Thus, in the methodology of comprehensive assessment of professional performance of a public civil servant «in the assessment of professional and personal qualities used such criteria as: 1) showed high organization; showed good organization; showed poor organization; 2) showed very high efficiency; showed high efficiency; showed low efficiency; showed low efficiency; showed very low efficiency. The absence of measurable quantitative and qualitative criteria entails their formal consideration and, most depressing of all, a subjective approach (exclusively by the immediate manager) to assessing their presence and manifestation» [38]. Public authorities, when implementing a comprehensive assessment of professional performance of a public civil servant, concretize the recommended assessments, keeping the formal description without specifying the content and measurement parameters. A necessary tool to overcome the existing contradiction in the system of state civil service and professional development of a civil servant should be the development of a unified methodology for the assessment of PLQ and the normative consolidation of considering the results of this assessment in the selection and implementation of the activities of state civil servants [40].

The theory and practice of public administration system development shows that the role of PLQ in the assessment of professional performance of public civil servants has not been properly developed to date. De facto, there is a priority of assessing professional competencies within the framework of the development of the competence approach without due consideration and specification of the PLQ of civil servants. This fact is explained by many factors, including the diversity of approaches to the development of assessment of professional performance of public civil servants [38], the duration of the introduction of new technologies, incomplete component of the methods of assessment of professional performance.

Review of theories and approaches to assessing professional and personal performance of civil servants.

The necessity to consider individual characteristics of personnel can be found in the works of A. Fayol [26, 34]. Having laid the foundations of scientific management, the scientist, among others, outlined the following qualities and knowledge that an employee should possess regardless of the level of his position: mental qualities, moral qualities, general development and special knowledge. Also A. Fayol [26] asserted that a top manager should have high volitional regulation and have certain abilities for the activity he realized.

Continuing F. Fayol's research, since 1924 the «school of human relations» [28] was actively developed, the postulate of which was that the degree of effectiveness of the organization depends on the effectiveness of human resources. At the same time, a special role was given to the needs of the individual, which determine the motivation of his / her production activity. The school of «human relations» was followed by the «school of behavioral sciences», in which a special place was also given to the study of motivation and leadership qualities of personnel, considering the role of social, age and other factors.

Further, from the middle of the XX century and up to the present time, also confirming the significance of considering the individual characteristics of the staff composition in organizational management, a new scientific trend «management school» or «school of quantitative methods» was formed. Thus, the existing theories confirm the position that the human factor is the most effective and inexhaustible resource in production activities and considering the socio-psychological characteristics of personnel is a necessary condition for improving the effectiveness of the organization.

The increasing role of human beings in the process of technical and socio-economic development has led to the emergence of ideas about personnel as a special value, a special type of capital and, therefore, the formation of the theory of «human capital». The key motive in this theory is the statement that «human capital is a socio-economic form of expression of productive qualities, properties, abilities, powers, functions and roles of a person included in the system of socially oriented economy of mixed type» [38].

The primary role, according to this theory, is given to a person as a carrier of this capital. Rethinking the role and importance of a person in the production process has led to the development of an independent direction of scientific knowledge «personnel management». In this direction the importance of studying and the need to consider professional (knowledge, skills, experience) and personal qualities (values, beliefs, abilities, motives, needs, etc.) of employees in organizational management is scientifically substantiated and does not raise doubts.

To solve the problem of effective selection and assessment of personnel it is necessary to use effective information about a candidate for a vacant position. However, to assess the candidate's compliance with the requirements of the activity he/she is applying for, it is necessary to have a comprehensive methodological toolkit that corresponds to the specifics of a particular activity in a particular organization, as well as to consider the professional and personal qualities of candidates. Development of such a methodological toolkit will allow solving the problem of qualitative personnel assessment and development. For this purpose, it is necessary to know the individual characteristics of the candidate that determine the success of his / her professional activity.

When developing such a toolkit, it is necessary to consider the subject-oriented and personality approaches. Personality characterizes an individual as a social being who possesses the following characteristics: temperament, gifts and abilities, motivation (orientation), character, status in society, will and feelings. Also, personality characteristics include mental properties (thinking, memory, attention, speech, imagination) as the most significant in the structure of all mental properties [36, 38]. Personnel assessment based on the study of the candidate's personality properties, conditioned by a specific activity, is necessary because it implies the determination of the features of the human activity management system.

Activity is a dynamic system of interaction between an individual and society. The motivating causes of human activity are attitudes, needs and motives. Motives are formed based on needs and motivate an individual to activity, determining its goals and objectives. Thus, human activity is always determined by needs and motives as inducing forces for the realization of this activity.

Human labor activity, regardless of its type (mental, physical, creative or intellectual) has a social character, as it is characterized by social significance. In addition, only by implementing labor activity an individual can take a certain position and role in society. The characteristic of labor activity is the mediated development of personality in the process of realization of activity. Thus, to predict the development of a person or his behavior, it is necessary to consider his personal characteristics, as well as the characteristics of the activity to be performed by a particular individual. However, professional assessment cannot be reduced only to the diagnosis of specific personal characteristics, it is necessary to assess the degree of development of integral psychological characteristics that determine the presence of certain qualities.

Professional and personal qualities are those individual-psychological properties of a person that determine the possibility of effective implementation of a particular type of professional activity. Professional activity, in turn, presupposes that an individual has certain abilities (general and special), which differ depending on the requirements of the profession.

Today, the competency model is widely used in the practice of professional assessment. The work of D. McClelland laid the foundation for the widespread growth of competencies. McClelland argued

that aptitude tests, which are almost universally used to predict occupational performance, do not serve their intended purpose and are subject to cultural bias. McClelland suggested that individual competence may provide more promising alternatives for predicting occupational performance [30].

At the current stage of development of the system of personnel assessment of civil servants' performance the method «360 degrees» is used. The method is aimed at diagnosing the level of professional skills required for effective performance of managers. The value of the method is that the assessment is carried out from «all» sides, i.e. all subjects of organizational relations: the manager, colleagues, subordinates, the employee himself. Also, by analogy with these methods, the method of assessment «540 degrees» is sometimes used, which implies the inclusion of subjects of external activity in the assessment.

Another equally popular method in assessment is the case study, which involves solving a certain task and is based on real-life situations. The distinctive feature of the case study method is the learning and developmental nature of diagnostics.

Also, in the practice of assessment, hardware diagnostic methods are widely used, which include the study of psychophysiological and individual-psychological determinants of personality: «Malakhit» (dermatoglyphics), «Activationometer», «AntistressBOS», «Photoplethysmograph», etc. [20]. To the methods that allow us to obtain information about individual characteristics of personality, we can include self-reporting / self-observation. However, these methods have a highly subjective nature of information and have several difficulties in conducting when it is necessary to survey a large group of respondents.

The most popular method of diagnosing personality in public administration today, despite all the variety of diagnostic tools, is the personality questionnaire, which allows you to get the most objective information about the personality.

In the Russian practice of assessment of civil servants, various aptitude tests (e.g., Amthauer Intelligence Structure Test (IST) and personality questionnaires (e.g., Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory (MMPI)) are mainly used. However, they do not allow obtaining comprehensive information about the peculiarities of the interrelation of the civil servants PLQ, but only private fragmentary data on one or another sphere of personality (intelligence, motivation, needs, competencies, etc.).

In foreign practice, the most common method of assessing professional and personal qualities of civil servants is a comprehensive method Hogan Assessment. The Hogan Assessment diagnostic includes three questionnaires consisting of a total of 600 questions. The methodology allows to study the personality characteristics manifested in professional activity and determining career orientations.

The following conclusions can be drawn based on the results of the review of various theories and approaches to the evaluation of public civil servants:

1) the development is moving towards the formation of competencies of state civil servants that meet the modern requirements of society;

2) in the civil service it is necessary to use technologies for assessing professional and personal qualities of public civil servants, which are based on the qualification requirements for the positions held in the civil service and correspond to the methodological principles of personality-oriented and competence-based approaches [4].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The relevance of the stated problem, as well as a review of modern theories and approaches to the evaluation of public civil servants allows us to formulate the purpose and objectives of the study. Objective: to develop a comprehensive system of assessment of professional and personal qualities of public civil servants in the system of public administration.

Objectives of the study:

- 1) to analyze the practice of assessment of professional and personal qualities of state civil servants in the system of public administration in the Russian Federation;
- 2) to study the normative legal support of assessment of professional and personal qualities of state civil servants in the Russian legislation;
- 3) to develop the basic principles of a comprehensive system of assessment of professional and personal qualities of state civil servants in the system of public administration.

The research method was theoretical analysis of scientific, educational, and periodical literature on the stated problem; analysis of the normative legal framework regulating the assessment of professional and personal qualities of public civil servants.

The federal laws of the Russian Federation and laws of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation, as well as other normative legal acts of the Russian Federation and constituent entities of the Russian Federation; the results of research of scientists and specialists on the issues of assessment of professional and personal qualities of public civil servants were used as information sources of the study.

The research was based on modern reference databases of peer-reviewed scientific literature: eLIBRARY.ru, lens.org; cross-platform reference legal system – ConsultantPlus.

As a result of the conducted research, the author's model of a comprehensive system of assessment of professional and personal qualities of civil servants has been developed, the implementation of which will make it possible to assess the level of professional development of civil servants; the compliance of the level of development of professional competencies with the required (occupied) position, as well as professional and personal potential for career growth. The practical significance of the study lies in the fact that the proposed model of a comprehensive system of assessment of professional and personal qualities of civil servants can be used in the practice of public administration to obtain objective data on the level of development of human resources for improving the system of public administration focused on the innovative development of the Russian economy.

RESULTS

Creation of a model of professionalism of a civil servant is a necessary basic assessment of professional and personal qualities of a civil servant. Evaluation always involves comparison with some model, which reflects the necessary for a modern civil servant professional and personal quality. Professionalism of a civil servant in modern civil service is considered from two positions: professionalism of civil servant's activity and professionalism of civil servant's personality [17].

Professionalism of activity includes the level of competence of a civil servant, his knowledge, skills, abilities, skills, and experience [36].

Professionalism of personality includes characteristics and features of personality spheres in the context of professional activity: motivational and semantic; emotional and sensual; socio-perceptive; cognitive (cognitive); organizational and communicative; anticipation (anticipation); operational and technological; autoregulatory [17].

Each of the designated spheres requires some model to assess the level of development of a civil servant and the success of his/her activity. In addition, a comprehensive assessment involves the analysis of life values and the system of motives for activity, external and internal factors that determine the success of the civil servant. The assessment methodology should contain a system of requirements to the structure and content of tools for assessing professional and personal qualities of civil servants.

Table 1 summaries the most common Russian practices and methods of professional performance evaluation of civil servants in Russia [5].

Table 1

Methods of assessing the professional performance of public civil servants (Bartsits, 2016)

Methods	Evaluation criteria
Personality Profile Assessment Methods	The essence of this method is that based on the use of such criteria as independence, concentration, decision-making ability, reliability, punctuality, it is determined to what extent a civil servant can solve professional tasks associated with the main role of the personality
Behavioral plan assessment method	This method evaluates the behavioral factors of public servants and produces an authority rating
Valuation method based on the analysis of the performance segment	The final assessment of professional and personal activity of an employee is the sum of the received points according to the results of quantitative assessment of tasks and results of their fulfillment.
Evaluation method based on job analysis	This method evaluates quantitative indicators of a public civil servant's performance

Other methods of evaluating the performance of civil servants are also used, such as the method of goal-oriented management, the method of graphic rating scale, the method of forced choice, the descriptive method and the method of questionnaires.

The method of management by objectives implies the use of quantitative assessment of goals and results of their achievement, as well as the costs of time, financial and material costs associated with the achievement of these goals. In the process of regular monitoring and discussion of the results of activity, the assessment of professionalism of a civil servant is formed, i.e. the ability to solve the set tasks with a minimum of resources. Thus, the effectiveness and efficiency of his/her activity is assessed. The complexity of the application of this method in practice is associated, first, with the problem of correctness of setting tasks and goals, measurability of goals and results, as well as the presence of the problem of objectivity of assessment in the process of control and monitoring of the process of achievement of goals by a civil servant. The multiplicity of goals and objectives, as well as the multiplicity of individual assessments of results causes the need to develop a system of indicators for assessing the results of achieving the goals of civil servants.

The method of scales s graphical rating implies the use of a rating scale from 0 to 4. An excellent result of a civil servant's performance is rated at «4», while an unsatisfactory one is rated at «0». This method is interesting because it allows to evaluate not only quantitative results of civil servants' activity, but also the quality of task fulfillment, considering various personal traits of a specialist, i.e. it evaluates how these results were achieved. Thus, it is possible to compare the personal character traits of a civil servant necessary to fill a particular position, for example, initiative, communication skills, reliability, decision-making ability, and others. A significant disadvantage of this method is the high subjectivity of the assessment.

The method of forced choice implies, first, the development of a system of necessary and characteristic for a particular civil servant, occupying a particular position and performing specific job duties, character qualities. These characteristics are assigned a weight in the degree of importance. The results of the employee's work are evaluated in points, and considering the weight of characteristics the index of performance efficiency is calculated. Again, a significant disadvantage and disadvantage of this method is the subjective nature of assessing the qualities of a specialist.

The descriptive method is widely used in the practice of assessment of civil servants' PLQ. During the civil servant's activity, his immediate supervisor could record the results of the civil servant's activity, his attitude to the work performed and duties, his daily behavior, as well as his reaction to arising non-standard situations. In accordance with a certain set of criteria reflect the achievements and failures of the civil servant in the performance of his duties and tasks assigned to him. This method, in accordance with its name, is based on the description of the civil servant's activities, his skills and abilities, strengths and weaknesses of the specialist, areas of activity where it is necessary to obtain additional competencies.

The questionnaire method is also widespread in the practice of public administration. By answering the questionnaire questions, the professional level and personal characteristics of civil servants are revealed, which allows to compare them with the necessary qualification requirements for civil service positions. The complexity of the application of this method relates to the need to develop correct questions of questionnaires that allow to reliably assess the personality of civil servants. The main disadvantage of the questionnaire method is also the subjective nature of the assessment.

The professional interview method is a procedure for identifying strategic thinking skills, coordination of managerial activities, managerial decision-making skills. When using this method, a structured interview with standardized, preformulated questions is developed. All questions should be related to the work and functions performed by the civil servant. The answers of civil servants are evaluated in points according to certain criteria. Later, the points are summarized and an assessment of the level of professional training and compliance of personal qualities with qualification requirements is given.

Thus, based on the definition of the features of professionalism of civil servants and components of professionalism of activity and professionalism of personality in general, all methods of assessing professional and personal qualities can be divided into two groups.

1. Methods to determine the level of professional training, level of knowledge, skills, and abilities of public civil servants. These methods are characterized using formal techniques and methods, such as testing, solving practical tasks, including such as, for example, the preparation of a draft regulatory act and others.

2. Methods that use psychological techniques aimed at identifying the personal characteristics of civil servants, such as interview, questionnaire, descriptive method, discussion, and others.

Despite the variety of assessment methods, the problem of formalism and subjective nature of the assessment itself remains relevant today. The choice of a particular method of assessment of state civil servants in a particular body of state or municipal management is determined by the goals and objectives of the assessment, as well as the existing approach to the assessment of civil servants' performance at the federal, regional, and regional levels, and the regulatory legal framework governing this process.

In the Russian Federation, the evaluation of state civil servants is regulated by a system of normative legal acts consisting of federal laws, laws of constituent entities of the Russian Federation, Resolutions of the Government of the Russian Federation, Decrees of the President of the Russian Federation, and others.

It should be noted that there is no special legal regulation and system of indicators for assessing professional and personal qualities of public civil servants. In this regard, the improvement of legal regulation in this area seems to be extremely important.

Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation of March 31, 2018, N. 397 «On Approval of the Unified Methodology for Conducting Competitions to Fill Vacant Positions in the Civil Service of the Russian Federation and for Inclusion in the Personnel Reserve of State Bodies» stipulates that in conducting competitions, the professional and personal qualities of candidates are assessed. This methodology defines key competencies for state civil servants categorized as «managers» and «specialists», namely: strategic thinking; teamwork; flexibility and readiness for change; personal efficiency; leadership; management decision-making [10].

Decree of the President of the Russian Federation of February 01, 2005, N.112 (ed. October 06, 2020) «On the competition to fill a vacant position in the civil service of the Russian Federation» defines the procedure for holding the competition [11].

Assessment of professional and personal qualities of candidates shall be carried out using various assessment methods, including individual interviews, questionnaires, group discussions, drafting a document, writing an essay and other written work, solving practical tasks or testing on issues related to the performance of job duties for a vacant civil service position.

Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation of March 05, 2018, N.227 «On Certain Measures to Introduce Information Technologies in Personnel Work in the Civil Service of the Russian

Federation» provides for the submission of an application for the submission of documents in electronic form (hereinafter – documents) by a candidate for participation in competitions: for the filling of a vacant position in the civil service of the Russian Federation and inclusion in the personnel reserve of a federal state body [9].

It should be noted that an effective method of assessing professional and personal qualities for their compliance with the planned position at the stage of application submission, in our opinion, can be testing of the candidate electronically on the unified portal of public services.

The legal basis for the implementation of the assessment of professional and personal qualities of the state is reflected in the Federal Law N 79-FL of July 27, 2004 «On the State Civil Service of the Russian Federation» [18].

Decree of the President of the Russian Federation of February 01, 2005, N 111 (ed. July 01, 2014) «On the Procedure for the Qualification Examination by State Civil Servants of the Russian Federation and Assessment of Their Knowledge, Skills and Abilities (Professional Level)» defines the procedure for taking the qualification examination [12].

In accordance with part 4 of Art. 48 of Federal Law N 79-FL provides for mandatory attestation for state civil servants once every three years [18]. Decree of the President of the Russian Federation of February 1, 2005, N 110 (ed. March 07, 2020) «On attestation of state civil servants of the Russian Federation» approved the Regulations on attestation of state civil servants of the Russian Federation [13].

Based on the results of attestation of state civil servants in accordance with part 15 of Article 48 of Federal Law N 79-FL, the attestation commission makes decisions on the compliance or non-compliance of a state civil servant to the position he/she is filling, on inclusion in the personnel reserve to fill a vacant civil service position; recommendations are given to a state civil servant to receive additional professional education [18].

During the attestation process, the civil servant's supervisor, in accordance with part 2 of Article 48 of Federal Law N 79-FL, submits a motivated review of the civil servant's performance of job duties [18].

To form a reasonable and comprehensive opinion of the head about the activities of a public civil servant and about the quality of performance of official duties in accordance with the job description, it is assumed to use scheduled and unscheduled assessments of professional and personal qualities of a public civil servant.

The Decree of the President of the Russian Federation of June 24, 2019, N 288 «On the main directions for the development of the state civil service of the Russian Federation for 2019 – 2021» [15], as well as the Order of the Government of the Russian Federation of July 24, 2019, N 1646-r «On approval of the action plan («road map») for the implementation of the main directions for the development of the state civil service of the Russian Federation for 2019 – 2021» [34], in order to further develop the state civil service of the Russian Federation provides:

- improving the procedure for appointing citizens of the Russian Federation and state civil servants of the Russian Federation to positions in the state civil service of the Russian Federation;
- incentivizing civil servants to improve the efficiency of their professional service activities, development of the system of state legal and social guarantees in the civil service;
- introduction of new forms of professional development of civil servants, including those involving the use of information and communication technologies;
- accelerated implementation of information and communication technologies in government agencies to improve the quality of human resources work.

The implementation of these areas implies the development of indicators of effectiveness and efficiency of their activities for each state civil servant. Based on the results of this assessment, it is possible to correlate the potential of state civil servants and the qualification requirements for the position, as well as to develop a long-term plan for development and promotion in accordance

with the Decree of the President of the Russian Federation of February 21, 2019, N 68 «On the professional development of state civil servants of the Russian Federation» [14]. This decree approved the «Regulations on the Procedure for the Professional Development of State Civil Servants of the Russian Federation».

The Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Russian Federation has developed a Methodological Toolkit for the implementation of a system of comprehensive assessment of the professional performance of state civil servants. An integral part of this toolkit is the Methodology for Comprehensive Assessment of the Professional Performance of a State Civil Servant.

Based on the Comprehensive Assessment Methodology developed by the Ministry of Labor of the Russian Federation, the manager shall prepare a review of the civil servant's performance of his / her official duties. The Comprehensive Evaluation Methodology contains an assessment of the performance of state civil servants on the parameters of efficiency and effectiveness of professional service activity, his qualifications, as well as professional and personal qualities or competencies.

Improvement of legal regulation in the field of assessment of professional and personal qualities of public civil servants should be based on the study and analysis of law enforcement practice; development of proposals to eliminate problems and controversial provisions of the legislation; preparation, development, and adoption of new normative legal acts [36].

For example, in accordance with the provisions of Federal Law N 79-FL «On State Civil Service of the Russian Federation» dated 27 July 2004, two types of indicators are envisaged for assessing the performance of state civil servants: generalized and specific. These indicators should be included in the job descriptions of civil servants [18].

The President of the Russian Federation and the Government of the Russian Federation approve generalized indicators of efficiency and effectiveness of the activities of state bodies, efficiency and effectiveness of adoption and implementation of managerial and other decisions, as well as legal, organizational, and documentary support for the implementation of these decisions. Specific indicators are developed and approved by a legal act of a state body in accordance with the peculiarities of its tasks and functions.

To date, there are no adopted normative legal acts regulating the inclusion of specific professional and personal qualities and indicators of their assessment in the job descriptions of civil servants, which would allow to assess the compliance of civil servants with the position held.

In accordance with part 8 of article 12 of Federal Law N 79-FL, the Russian Ministry of Labor has developed and regularly updates the Handbook of qualification requirements for specialties, areas of training, knowledge and skills that are necessary to fill civil service positions, considering the field and type of professional service activities of civil servants (hereinafter – the Handbook).

Approaches and recommendations for the application of this Handbook are determined by the Methodological Toolkit on the establishment of qualification requirements for civil service positions. The use of the Handbook is envisaged for the formation of qualification requirements for civil service positions and the development of due regulations, which should include qualification requirements for civil service positions, formed considering the areas and types of activities. These qualification requirements are considered during personnel procedures and in assessing the professional level of civil servants.

Thus, based on the results of the analysis of the system of normative legal regulation of the process of assessment of professional and personal qualities, it is established that this system is imperfect and requires further development to define the methods, procedures and results of assessment more clearly.

The above-mentioned practices of assessment of personal and professional qualities of public civil servants, as well as the normative legal support of this activity allow us to conclude about the effectiveness of their use in the implementation of personnel policy in the civil service.

First, the use of this assessment ensures the realization of the principle of meritocracy, which implies promotion and career growth of an employee solely depending on his personal and professional qualities and his professional development.

Secondly, the assessment of personal and professional qualities allows to identify the characteristics of civil servants and determine their suitability for their position, as well as to plan the further development of civil servants in terms of improving their managerial and professional competencies.

Table 2 shows the system of comprehensive assessment of civil servants in various procedures. As can be seen, the system of comprehensive assessment includes the assessment of personal and professional qualities.

Table 2

System of comprehensive assessment of civil servants

Selection procedure	Questionnaire data	Basic competencies	Professional-functional competencies	Personal competencies
Competition to fill a vacant position	+	+	+	+
Competition for inclusion in the personnel reserve	+	+	+	+
Attestation	+	-	+	+
Recruitment from the talent pool	+	+	+	+
Recruitment of staff without competitive bidding	+	+	+	+

Table 3 presents a model of civil servants' competencies reflecting their personal and professional qualities.

Table 3

Competency model for civil servants

Highest and main group of posts	Managers Assistants (advisors) Specialists	Managerial institutional competencies	
Main group of posts	Supporting professionals	↑ Master's degree Advanced specialization Professional-functional competencies ↑	
Leading group	Managers		
	Assistants (advisors)		
	Specialists	Qualification requirements for professional knowledge	Qualification requirements for professional skills
Senior group	Specialists	↑	↑
		Bachelor's degree Primary professional competencies	

This model reflects the requirements for professional skills and abilities in accordance with the groups of positions and the required level of education. This model is the basis of the Handbook of qualification requirements for specialties, areas of training, knowledge and skills that are necessary to fill positions of the state civil service, considering the field and type of professional service activity of state civil servants.

These qualification requirements, reflected in the Handbook, form the basis for the development of job descriptions. These regulations reflect the basic requirements for personal and professional qualities of candidates for the relevant positions of the state civil service. Possession of such competencies allows citizens to perform official duties for civil service positions.

Summarizing the existing experience of assessing professional and personal qualities, it is more appropriate to talk about personal and professional diagnostics of civil servants, allowing to assess and reveal their potential.

At the same time, it should be noted that the diagnosis of personal and professional qualities should be not just a set of methods and techniques that allow to conduct a specific assessment of quality and / or performance, to solve a local problem. Rather, it should be a holistic conceptual system of diagnostics, capable of identifying civil servants who meet the requirements of success, efficiency, and effectiveness in the context of their activities.

The effective organization of diagnostics of personal and professional qualities of public civil servants involves the use of various assessment mechanisms: legal, organizational, and substantive.

Organizational mechanisms of diagnostics of personal and professional qualities of state civil servants are based on the assessment procedure during attestation, competition, formation of reserve and rotation.

Numerous empirical studies suggest that when assessing the personal and professional qualities of public civil servants, it is necessary to use different methods and procedures for assessing public servants occupying different positions.

Three groups of posts are useful for utilizing different evaluation procedures:

- 1) «Executives» – characterized by scope and a high level of personal responsibility;
- 2) «Assistants – advisors» – expert-analytical work and organizational work;
- 3) «Specialists» – «specialists» of the highest, main and leading groups of positions. Here it is advisable to form several functional zones and assess personal and professional qualities in accordance with the following categories «analytics», «organization», «communication» and «control».

An important condition for the effectiveness of the assessment is the establishment of a set of indicators for each group and a way to translate these indicators into assessment tools.

For example, when assessing groups of top positions, the «Commission under the President of the Russian Federation has approved a system of quantitative indicators for assessing the management personnel reserve, which includes the following: 1) Strategic Leadership; 2) Social focus; 3) Managerial readiness; 4) Scale of thinking; 5) Willingness to learn and develop; 6) Readiness for teamwork; 7) Perseverance and commitment; 8) Communicative competence; 9) Self-Governance competencies; 10) Legal and professional knowledge in the field of public service and management.

Qualitative evaluation indicators include the identification and description of the strongest strengths, identification of personal and individual-psychological characteristics that require attention and consideration in the communication process, as well as recommended trajectories and directions of professional development of civil servants.

Such personal-professional diagnostics also makes it possible to identify the sphere of activity of the assessed applicant, in which, considering his personal and individual-psychological features, as well as the level of professional training, he would show himself most effectively.

Table 4 shows a grouping of professional and personal qualities, which, in our opinion, according to the results of the study, should be possessed by civil servants belonging to different groups of positions.

Table 4

Pool of professional and personal qualities of civil servants

Positions of the state civil service	Managers	Assistants
Professional and personal qualities	Activity, ambitiousness, visionary, diplomacy, initiative, creativity, teamwork, communication, leadership, objectivity, responsibility, consistency, entrepreneurship, insightfulness, decisiveness, self-organization, fairness, stress resilience, demanding, confidence.	Activity, attentiveness, conscientiousness, initiative, teamwork, communication skills, independence, learnability, objectivity, responsibility, consistency, workability, self-organization, stress-resistance.

Positions of the state civil service	Specialists	Supporting professionals
Professional and personal qualities	Accuracy, attentiveness, discipline, initiative, diligence, executive ability, teamwork, communication skills, perseverance, non-conflict, learning ability, organized, responsibility, punctuality, workability, discretion, self-organization, conscientiousness, poise, purposefulness, honesty.	Accuracy, courtesy, attentiveness, well-manneredness, discipline, friendliness, conscientiousness, diligence, culture, non-conflict, learnability, organizational, responsibility, openness, integrity, punctuality, workability, self-organization, conscientiousness, poise, honesty.

In this regard, it is necessary to use different tools to assess different categories and groups of civil service positions.

The analysis of the Russian practice of assessment of civil servants and regulatory legal support of this activity has shown that the development of the state civil service in the Russian Federation should be associated primarily with the introduction of new personnel technologies in the system of public administration and management. These mechanisms will create a platform for identifying, attracting, and promoting the best trained and promising personnel, as well as candidates from among talented young people. In this regard, the system-forming element of improving the system of public administration and management is to increase the requirements not only to the experience and skills, but also to the personal and professional qualities of public civil servants.

A comprehensive system of assessment of the civil servants PLQ forms the most suitable from the point of view of the goals and objectives of the state body or its structural subdivision perspective plan for promotion to public service positions, as well as the selection of highly qualified personnel for public service. The assessment of public civil servants' PLQ implies the creation of a universal personality profile of a public civil servant, revealing the structure of personal and professional qualities necessary for a certain type of activity.

Methodological foundations of the comprehensive system of assessment of professional and personal qualities of public civil servants should include modern effective practices in the field of assessment of public civil servants and HR-technologies used in leading Russian and international companies. In our opinion, the following author's approaches can serve as a methodological basis for the development of a comprehensive system of assessment of civil servants' professional and personal qualities.

1. Hogan Assessment, which includes three questionnaires [22]. The first questionnaire is called the Hogan Personality Inventory (HPI) 1 and contains 266 questions, the answers to which are rated as true or false. The HPI is assessed on 7 major scales: adaptation, ambition, sociability, interpersonal sensitivity, cautiousness, curiosity, and educational orientation. The second questionnaire, the Hogan Developmental Study (HDS), contains 168 questions and assesses 11 behaviors in challenging situations. The third questionnaire, the Hogan Motivation, Values and Personality Inventory (MVPI), examines a person's motivation and values: what kind of work he or she likes to do, what he or she prefers to do and what he or she will do to achieve the ultimate career goal, what he or she is oriented toward in activities and relationships. The Hogan Complex also uses the Hogan 360 Test, which measures a person's reputation in the workplace.

2. The Sixteen Personality Factor Questionnaire (16PF) is a 16-factor questionnaire aimed at studying individual psychological features of personality [8]. It involves the study of relatively independent 16 factors (primary traits) of personality, which form a group of four primary factors: a group of communicative properties; a group of intellectual properties; a group of emotional properties; a group of regulatory properties.

3. The Myers-Briggs Type Indicator 1, developed back in the 1940s based on C. Jung's personality typology [19, 31]. Here, personality assessment is based on questions about a person's preferences in four areas corresponding to four scales: extraversion (E) – introversion (I); feeling (S) – intuition (N); judgment (J) – perception (P); thinking (T) – feeling (F) (rationality – irrationality) and the results are combined into one of 16 possible types. The complex system of assessment of civil servants' PLQ should include factors of personal and professional characteristics, the diagnosis

of which will allow to describe the portrait of a civil servant and get a predictive character of the assessment of the performance of his professional activity. Thus, the model of a comprehensive system of assessment of civil servants' PLQ should include blocks of personal and professional factors, each of which includes differentiating scales and a common for the two blocks scale «Credibility and reliability of data» (Table 5).

In determining the blocks of personal and professional factors along with the above listed author's approaches, we also used scientific developments of complex technology of personal and professional diagnostics and assessment of managerial personnel, resource, and competence approaches, as well as the acmeological approach of Derkach A., Zazykin V. O. and Markova A. K. in terms of determining the substructures of professional characteristics and acmeological invariants of professionalism [17].

Each block of factors includes personal and professional characteristics that determine the performance of public civil servants. The level of civil servants' position will be used as an indicator of the performance of public civil servants: the category of «Managers» and the category of «Specialists».

Table 5

Personal and professional factors of the complex system of assessment of public civil servants

Scales	Personality Factors Block	Occupational factors block
1	<i>Data reliability and validity scale</i>	
	Reliability Of Answers Openness Honesty	
2	<i>Self-esteem</i>	<i>Operational and technological</i>
	Self-concept Self-awareness Critical thinking	Decision-making and implementation skills Performance level Managerial skills Organizational style
3	<i>Intellectual sphere</i>	<i>Social perceptual</i>
	Creative thinking and creativity Susceptibility Flexibility Emotional intelligence Broadmindedness Openness to new things	Locus of control (External / Internal) Tendency to conformism in professional activities Social mobility / adaptability
4	<i>Communicative sphere</i>	<i>Cognitive</i>
	Sociability Initiative Courage Openness Autonomy Diplomacy	Professional competence Professional knowledge and skills Professional creativity and creativity Coping strategies
5	<i>Emotional sphere</i>	<i>Organizational and communicative</i>
	Stress tolerance Adaptability Anxiety Tension Empathy	Personal and business qualities Level of readiness for teamwork Features of communications in the activity Leadership skills
6	<i>Volitional regulation</i>	<i>Emotional-sensitive</i>
	Focus on results Discipline Time management skills Planning, organization, and coordination Precision and attention to detail Adaptability Autonomy Determination	Self-awareness / self-image in professional activities Risk appetite Professional empathy

7	<i>Value and meaning sphere</i>	<i>Motivational and semantic</i>
	Normativity Humanity Culturedness Spirituality Hedonism Honesty Altruism Freedom	Striving to achieve high-level professional results Eagerness to learn and self-development Orientation to problem solving in professional activities Striving for safety in professional activities
8	<i>Motivation and needs sphere</i>	<i>Anticipation</i>
	Achievement motivation Avoidance motivation Social acceptance motives Social recognition motives Motives of power Service motivation Altruistic motives Self-development motivation Cognitive needs Material needs Need for security Needs for social belonging Aesthetic needs Needs for recognition and respect	Predictive ability Having strategic goals and objectives

Determination of the methodological basis of the complex system of assessment of professional and personal qualities of public civil servants, including blocks of personal and professional factors, differentiating scales, the general scale of «Reliability and reliability of data» will allow to develop a diagnostic toolkit for assessing the PLQ of public civil servants that meets the requirements of validity, reliability and validity of data in order to collect information necessary for solving personnel issues and management activities in general. The developed assessment system will allow to form a personality profile of a public civil servant (or candidate for public civil service) and provide recommendations on the need to develop this or that area of knowledge, skills, abilities or competencies.

Creation of a comprehensive system of assessment of professional and personal qualities of public civil servants and its further testing by interviewing public civil servants and managers of different levels of government will be carried out in further research. The results of the assessment can be used to create a personnel reserve or to make personnel decisions.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Within the framework of the conducted research the following results were obtained:

1) Modern theories and approaches to the assessment of professional and personal qualities of state civil servants have been considered. Modern trends of diagnostics and assessment of state civil servants have been revealed;

2) Analyzed the normative legal support of activities aimed at assessing the professional and personal qualities of civil servants. The conclusions are made that the system of normative legal framework regulating the assessment of civil servants is aimed more at the assessment of quantitative indicators (performance results); assessment of the knowledge component of civil servants and competencies. Whereas the substantive issues related to personal and professional qualities of civil servants in accordance with the priority areas of activity remain open. In this regard, the comprehensive system of assessment of public civil servants requires further development in order to better define the methods, procedures and results of assessment;

3) The model of the complex system of assessment of professional and personal qualities of public civil servants, including blocks of personal and professional factors, each of which contains

differentiating scales of assessment and common for two blocks assessment scale «Validity and reliability of data» is developed.

The results of the theoretical study are aimed at the development of public administration system in the field of certification of civil servants; organization of professional training and development of civil servants; organization of personnel reserve, as well as organizational and methodological support of other personnel measures in the system of public administration.

LIMITATIONS AND SHORTCOMINGS OF THE STUDY

This article presents the results of a theoretical study of the problem of assessing the performance effectiveness of public civil servants. It is established that this assessment should include the diagnosis of personal and professional qualities of public civil servants and the author's model of comprehensive assessment of the PLQ of public civil servants is proposed. However, to determine the effectiveness of the developed model it is necessary to carry out its approbation. Approbation of the model now is realized by conducting a survey of civil servants and managers of various levels of executive power. The results of approbation will be presented in further scientific research of the research team.

FUNDING

The article was prepared within the framework of realization of the RSF grant № 23-28-01537 «Diagnostics of professional and personal qualities of managerial personnel: methodology and technologies».

REFERENCES

1. Albrecht, J., Robayo-Abril M., Vroman S. (2018). Public-Sector Employment in an Equilibrium Search and Matching Model. *Economic Journal*, 129(617), 35–61.
2. Aleshko, R., Petrova, L., Ivanova, E., Plotnikova, A., Melnikov, M., Antonov, V. (2019). Human capital in the digital economy format. *Int. J. Eng. Adv. Technol.*, 9, 7517-7523.
3. Anikin V. A., Antonov E. V., Antonova V. K. et al. (2023). Human potential: modern interpretations and research results. Moscow: All-Russian Centre for the Study of Public Opinion. (in Russ.)
4. Altermark, N., Johansson, H. & Stattin, S. Shaping Civil Society Leaders: Horizontal and Vertical Boundary Work in Swedish Leadership Training Programmes. *Voluntas* 34, 1025–1035 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11266-022-00519-x>
5. Bartsits, I. N. (2016). Indicators of the performance of a civil servant. System of state and municipal government. Moscow: Meaning. (in Russ.)
6. Borshchevskiy, G.A. (2024). Federal personnel reserve of civil service as the closing element of the cadre vertical. *Public Administration Issues*, 2, pp. 7–40. DOI: 10.17323/1999-5431-2024-0-2-7-40. (in Russ.)
7. Butashin, D.A. (2021). Patterns of formation and development of public administration personnel. *Economics: yesterday, today, tomorrow*, 11(1A), 83-91. DOI: 10.34670/AR.2021.90.59.009 (in Russ.)
8. Cattell, H., & Mead, A. (2008). The sixteen-personality factor questionnaire (16pf). In *The SAGE Handbook of Personality Theory and Assessment: Volume 2 – Personality Measurement and Testing* (pp. 135-159). SAGE Publications Ltd, <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781849200479>
9. Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation dated 03.05.2018 No. 227 «On Certain Measures to Introduce Information Technologies in Personnel Work in the Civil Service of the Russian Federation» // Official Internet portal of legal information Available at: <http://www.pravo.gov.ru> (accessed September 2024). (in Russ.)
10. Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation dated 03.31.2018 No. 397 «On Approval of the Unified Methodology for Conducting Competitions to Fill Vacant Positions in the Civil Service of the Russian Federation and for Inclusion in the Personnel Reserve of State Bodies» // Official Internet portal of legal information Available at: <http://www.pravo.gov.ru> (accessed September 2024). (in Russ.)
11. Decree of the President of the Russian Federation dated 02.01.2005 No. 112 (ed. October 06, 2020) «On the competition to fill a vacant position in the civil service of the Russian Federation» // Official Internet portal of legal information Available at: <http://www.pravo.gov.ru> (accessed September 2024). (in Russ.)
12. Decree of the President of the Russian Federation dated 02.01.2005 No. 111 (ed. July 01, 2014) «On

- the Procedure for the Qualification Examination by State Civil Servants of the Russian Federation and Assessment of Their Knowledge, Skills and Abilities (Professional Level)» // Official Internet portal of legal information Available at: <http://www.pravo.gov.ru> (accessed September 2024). (in Russ.)
13. Decree of the President of the Russian Federation dated 02.01.2005 No. 110 (ed. March 07, 2020) «On attestation of state civil servants of the Russian Federation» // Official Internet portal of legal information Available at: <http://www.pravo.gov.ru> (accessed September 2024). (in Russ.)
 14. Decree of the President of the Russian Federation dated 21.02.2019 No. 68 «On the Professional Development of State Civil Servants of the Russian Federation» (together with the 'Regulations on the Procedure for the Professional Development of State Civil Servants of the Russian Federation') // Official Internet portal of legal information Available at: <http://www.pravo.gov.ru> (accessed September 2024). (in Russ.)
 15. Decree of the President of the Russian Federation dated 06.24.2019 No. 288 «On the main directions for the development of the state civil service of the Russian Federation for 2019 – 2021» // Official Internet portal of legal information Available at: <http://www.pravo.gov.ru> (accessed September 2024). (in Russ.)
 16. Demissie, A.D., Alemu, A.E. & Tensay, A.T. Servant Leadership and Organizational Citizenship Behavior: The Mediating Role of Perceived Organizational Politics and the Moderating Role of Political Skill in Public Service Organizations. *Employee Responsibilities and Rights Journal* (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10672-023-09486-x>
 17. Derkach, A. A., Bekhter A. A., Gagarin A. V. et al. (2019). Professional development: new approaches in integrative studies of personality. Moscow: Limited Liability Company. Publishing House: Knorus. (in Russ.)
 18. Federal Law dated 07.27.2004 No. 79-FL «On the State Civil Service of the Russian Federation» // Official Internet portal of legal information Available at: <http://www.pravo.gov.ru> (accessed September 2024). (in Russ.)
 19. Furnham A. (2020). Myers-briggs type indicator (mbti), *Encyclopedia of personality and individual differences*, pp. 3059–3062.
 20. Gorobets, T. N. et al. (2018). Prescriptive model "Psychophysiological predictors of managerial readiness of a manager. *Human Capital*, 9(117), 115–124. (in Russ.)
 21. Hatchuel, A., Segrestin, B. (2020). A century old and still visionary: Fayol's innovative theory of management. *European Management Review*, 16(2), 399–412.
 22. Hogan, R., & Hogan, J. (1992). *Hogan Personality Inventory manual*. Tulsa, OK: Hogan Assessment Systems.
 23. Khan, N.U., Zhongyi, P., Han, H. et al. (2023). Linking public leadership and public project success: the mediating role of team building. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10, 286. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-01791-y>
 24. Komissarov, A.G. and Sheburakov, I.B. (2024). Personnel reserves in the public administration system: Experience and new meanings. *Public Administration Issues*, 1, 7–38. DOI: 10.17323/1999-5431-2024-0-1-7-38.
 25. Kaselis M., Pivoras S. (2012). Civil Servants' Performance Assessment by Results: Challenges of Implementation in Lithuania. *Public Policy and Administration*, 11(1), 139–152.
 26. Lameck, W.U. (2024). Uncovering the potentials for public service motivation in Tanzania. *SN Social Sciences*, 4, 158. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43545-024-00958-x>
 27. Lobkova, E.V. and Khudonogova, E.R. (2024). On the issue of evaluating the effectiveness and performance of public civil servants: The experience of the Krasnoyarsk State Statistics Service. *Public Administration Issues*, 3, pp. 39–80. DOI: 10.17323/1999-5431-2024-0-3-39-80. (in Russ.)
 28. Mbalamula, Yazidu & Suru, Majiyd. (2023). Contextualizing Fayol's 14 principles in managing school systems in Tanzania. *International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 15, 64-70. 10.5897/IJEAPS2023.0751.
 29. McCall, M. W., & Hollenbeck, G. P. (2002). *Developing global executives: The lessons of international experience*. Boston: Harvard Business School Press.
 30. McClelland, D. C. (1976). *The achieving society*. New York, NY: Irvington Publishers.
 31. Myers I. B. (1962). *The myers-briggs type indicator: Manual*. Consulting Psychologists Press.
 32. Nezhina T., Barabashev A., Prokofiev V., Utkina V. (2021). Public Personnel Job Satisfaction and Retention: The Effects of Perceived Image and Prestige of Government Jobs. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 44(16), 1435–1445. DOI: 10.1080/01900692.2021.1939714.
 33. Olishevych, M. & Stasyshyn, A. & Kravchuk, M. (2024). The Dynamic Scenarios of Development of the Innovative Segment of Public Administration. *Business Inform*, 2, 81-90. 10.32983/2222-4459-2024-2-81-90.
 34. Order of the Government of the Russian Federation dated 07.24.2019 No. 1646-r «On approval of the action plan («road map») for the implementation of the main directions for the development of the state civil service of the Russian Federation for 2019 – 2021» // Official Internet portal of legal information Available at: <http://www.pravo.gov.ru> (accessed September 2024). (in Russ.)
 35. Palchyk H. (2020). The System of Certification and Performance Evaluation of Civil Servants in the Republic of Belarus. *The International Journal of Civil Service Reform and Practice*, 5, 14, (2). URL: <https://astanahubjournal.org/index.php/ijcsrp/article/view/148>
 36. Pereverzeva, A. A., Shuklinova, M. V. (2016). Organization of assessment and diagnosis of professional and personal qualities of state civil servants. *Socio-economic phenomena and processes*, 11(9), 76-81. (in Russ.)

37. Polyakova, A. (2020). Civil Service, HR Potential, and Open Innovation. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 6(4), 1747 <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc6040174>
38. Sinyagin, Yu. V. (2019). Social orientation as a personality characteristic of the head of the civil service. *Personality education*, 1, 44. (in Russ.)
39. Uvarov, S. A., Kuchumov, A. V., Testina, Ya. S. (2018). Problems and prospects for using blockchain in the tourism industry. *Journal of Legal and Economic Research*, 4, 209-216. (in Russ.)
40. Venturini, K., Capaldo, G., Palazzi, F., Amatori, Ch., Capicchioni, A. (2024). Action learning in public administration education: learning (evidence) from an action research case study. *Journal of Workplace Learning*, 36(6), 443-459. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JWL-01-2024-0005>

Авторы

Салахова Валентина Борисовна

(Москва, Россия)

Кандидат психологических наук, ведущий научный сотрудник центра аналитических исследований и моделирования в образовании НИИ Урбанистики и глобального образования Московский городской педагогический университет

Ведущий научный сотрудник, Центр исследования проблем безопасности Российской академии наук (ЦИПБ РАН)

E-mail: salakhovavb@mgpu.ru
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5056-6518
Scopus Author ID: 56518287500

Кидинов Алексей Васильевич

(Москва, Россия)

Доктор психологических наук, доцент, профессор департамента психологии и развития человеческого капитала, Финансовый университет при Правительстве Российской Федерации;

профессор факультета коммуникативного менеджмента, Российский государственный социальный университет
E-mail: a080ak@gmail.com
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-1826-208X
Scopus Author ID: 57209731787

Бабиева Нигина Сафоевна

(Москва, Россия)

Кандидат психологических наук, доцент кафедры педагогики и медицинской психологии, Первый Московский государственный медицинский университет имени И. М. Сеченова Минздрава России (Сеченовский Университет)

E-mail: n.s.babieva@mail.ru
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-8076-3494
Scopus Author ID: 57194714913

Authors

Valentina B. Salakhova

(Russia, Moscow)

Cand. Sci. (Psychology), Leading Researcher, Research Institute of Urbanism and Global Education
Moscow City University

Leading Researcher of Centre for Security Studies of the Russian Academy of Sciences

E-mail: salakhovavb@mgpu.ru
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5056-6518
Scopus Author ID: 56518287500

Alexey V. Kidinov

(Russia, Moscow)

Dr. Sci. (Psychology), Associate Professor, Professor of the Department of Psychology and Human Capital Development
Financial University under the Government of the Russian Federation

Professor of the Department of Communication Management
Russian State Social University
E-mail: a080ak@gmail.com
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-1826-208X
Scopus Author ID: 57209731787

Nigina S. Babieva

(Russia, Moscow)

Cand. Sci. (Psychology), Associate Professor, Department of Pedagogy and Medical Psychology
I. M. Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University

E-mail: n.s.babieva@mail.ru
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-8076-3494
Scopus Author ID: 57194714913

Вклад авторов

Салахова В. Б.
Кидинов А. В.
Бабиева Н. С.

Author's contribution

Valentina B. Salakhova
Alexey V. Kidinov
Nigina S. Babieva

© Салахова В. Б., Кидинов А. В., Бабиева Н. С., 2025

© Valentina B. Salakhova, Alexey V. Kidinov, Nigina S. Babieva, 2025

Авторы заявляют об отсутствии конфликта интересов

The author's declared no conflicts of interest